

Health Insurance- Analytical Study with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

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Abstract:

The idea behind health insurance is that a collection of individuals who share a common risk pool together and contribute to the creation of a fund pool. The impact is enormous and unimaginable, and the consequences for millions of people's livelihoods will be disastrous. A pandemic raises awareness of insurance and the financial risks that can result in reduced income and higher costs. The rising number of deaths brought on by the COVID pandemic has increased public awareness of insurance options. Investing in health insurance is becoming increasingly important in light of the soaring expenses of medical care. It is one of the fastest-growing industries since it offers both financial security and insurance against medical costs, both before and after hospital stays. Numerous health firms in India provide inexpensive Mediclaim plans at a reasonable cost for both individuals and families. This paper elucidates the necessity of health insurance. This will help both public and private companies by providing a range of insurance options and raising public awareness of their advantages. Insurance offers risk transfer methods that allow third parties to take the risk associated with company activities, allowing businesses to operate in a cost-effective manner. Insurance is essential to people in the non-commercial sphere as well. Families and individuals without insurance would be vulnerable to daily life's uncertainties and lack of protection.

Key Words: Insurance, Mediclaim.

Introduction

In India, health insurance has only been around for a few decades. But despite this, it has a long history, as evidenced by Manu's writings. It is discussed how resource sharing is beneficial in times of disaster like fires, floods, and diseases. The idea of health insurance was initially proposed in 1694 by Hugh the Elder Chamberlin, a member of the Peter Chamberlin family. Thus, in the 19th century, "Accident Assurance" became accessible. However, new health insurance systems

replaced traditional disability insurance in the middle to late 20th century. Following that, with numerous modifications and advancements, health Insurance was created. India has made significant progress in the last 50 years with regard to health insurance. Look back at the state of Primary healthcare was prioritized after independence and saw significant advancements. An employee's state insurance plan (ESIS) was introduced in 1948, marking the beginning of health insurance in India. It was first developed as a social security safety net for organized sector blue-collar workers. It offers medical services via a network of hospitals and clinics that have partnered with ESIS. OPD and IPD costs, as well as cash benefits to make up for missed income and other medical eventualities, are covered under ESIS. This program is still in use and is primarily funded by contributions from both companies and employees. A central government health scheme (CGHS) initiative was also created in 1954. It was a contributory health plan designed to offer complete medical treatment, particularly to families and employees of the central government. Depending on their pay range, central government employees and the Indian government also donate a small sum each month which is still going well.

Statement of the problem:

In India, the health insurance market is growing in popularity. Health insurance is currently one of India's developing industries. Indian consumers become the most involved and proactive when it comes to health insurance, according to several ecosystem stakeholders, including private health insurance businesses. Purchasing cashless health insurance online is now commonplace following the pandemic. Rising medical costs, scientific breakthroughs, pandemics, and serious illnesses are the causes of this growing focus and awareness. The accessibility of health insurance plans for expecting mothers, children, and senior persons has increased public acceptance of medical insurance. As a result, the Indian health insurance market has created profitable growth paths and chances for both businesses and clients. Insurance plans must appeal to and satisfy policyholders in a variety of ways. Health insurance has today become a mainstay of any market economy since it offer plenty of scope for garnering large sums of money for long periods of time.

Objectives of the study

- To study the awareness and knowledge on health insurance policies among the policy holders in Coimbatore.
- To identify the factors that influencing the policy holders to avail the health insurance

policy in Coimbatore.

- To analyses the satisfaction level of health Insurance policies among the policy holders in Coimbatore.

Research methodology:

Sampling technique:

Sampling type:

For this study the researchers selected for convenient sampling method.

Sampling size:

Data Collection: Primary Data was collected from the respondents of Coimbatore by using convenience sampling methodology. A total of 100 questionnaires were distributed and gathered from the participants in the study. The Data was collected through questionnaire survey method. Results indicate that people start valuing the importance of insurance policies and their benefits.

Secondary data was collected through various magazines and other websites

Tools: Simple percentage analysis is used for this present study.

TABLE.1

Classification Of Respondent

GROUP	STATUS	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
GENDER	MALE	33	33
	FEMALE	67	67
	TOTAL	100	100
AGE	BELOW18	18	18
	18-30	52	52
	31-45	26	26
	46-60	3	3
	ABOVE 60	1	1
	TOTAL	100	100

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	NO FORMAL EDUCATION	35	35
	SCHOOL LEVEL	45	45
	UNDER GRADUATE	16	16
	POST GRADUATE	4	4
	TOTAL	100	100
OCCUPATIONAL STATUS	SELF EMPLOYED	30	30
	PRIVATE EMPLOYEE	49	49
	PUBLIC EMPLOYEE	16	16
	PROFESSIONAL	4	4
	STUDENT	1	1
	TOTAL	100	100
MARITAL STATUS	MARRIED	79	79
	SINGLE	21	21
	TOTAL	100	100
TYPEOFFAMILY	NUCLEAR FAMILY	72	72
	JOINT FAMILY	28	28
	TOTAL	100	100
MONTHLYFAMILYINCOME	BELOW20000	24	24
	20000-40000	53	53
	40000-60000	21	21
	60000-80000	2	2
	TOTAL	100	100

Interpretation

- As per the data given GENDER of the respondents 33% are male and 67% are female. Here, majority of the respondents are female.
- In the AGE minority of the respondents are above 60 and majority of the respondents are 18-30.
- In the EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION minority of the respondents are post graduate and majority of the respondents are school level.
- In the OCCUPATIONAL STATUS minority of the respondents are students and majority of the respondents are private employee.

- In the MARITALSTATUS of the respondents 21% are single and79% are married. Here, majority of the respondents are married.
- In the TYPE OF FAMILY minority of the respondents are joint family and majority of the respondents are nuclear family.
- In the MONTHLY FAMILY INCOME minority of the respondents are 60000-80000 and majority of the respondents are 20000-40000.

TABLE.2
Health Insurance Policy

ATTRIBUTES	NOOF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	87	87
NO	13	13
TOTAL	100	100

INTERPRETATION

According to the study, 87% of the respondents are having health insurance and13% of the respondents are not having health insurance.

TABLE.3

How Much Do You Care About Having A Health Insurance Policy?

ATTRIBUTES	NO.OFRESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
VERY MUCH	87	87
NOT MUCH	13	13
TOTAL	100	100

Interpretation

Here, 87% of the respondents are very much care about having a health insurance policy and 13% is not much care about having a health insurance policy.

TABLE.4

ARE YOU ABLE TO SMOOTHLY PAY YOUR CURRENT HEALTH INSURANCE POLICY

ATTRIBUTES	NO.OFRESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
YES	79	79
NO	21	21
TOTAL	100	100

Interpretation

In this 79% of the respondents are able to smoothly pay current health insurance policy and 21% of the respondents are not able to pay.

WHAT KIND OF HEALTH INSURANCE ARE YOU HIGHLY SATISFIED?

S.NO	ATTRIBUTES		EXCELLENT	VERY GOOD	GOOD	FAIR	POOR
1	WHOLE FAMILY HEALTH INSURANCE	NO	98	1	1	0	0
		%	98	1	1	0	0
2	FATHER/MOTHER HEALTH INSURANCE	NO	71	27	2	0	0
		%	71	27	2	0	0
3	SPOUSE HEALTH INSURANCE	NO	88	4	7	0	0
		%	88	4	7	0	0

4	INDIVIDUAL HEALTH INSURANCE	NO	76	6	15	3	0
		%	76	6	15	3	0

Interpretation

As we seen in this table highly respondents are whole family health insurance with 98% are the majority of respondents and father/mother health insurance with 71% of respondents and spouse health insurance with 88% of respondents and individual health insurance with 76% of respondents.

Suggestions

- The company should create more awareness programmed regarding health insurance via digital campaign.
- The company may give a wide service in the customers and maintain the attractive advertisement in social media.
- Though policy holders rate overall awareness to be good, but the depth of knowledge about product/scheme, exclusions and claims process were not adequate, further, the less educated people have lower levels of awareness about health insurance. Advertisements such as news papers, news items are the most widely reported sources of information, followed by television advertisement and insurance advisers/agents. Insurance advisers/agents being a relied source can be used to create insurers specific preference by promoting its products. There is more opportunity here as the marketing professionals with the health insurance do not focus adequately due to low returns with sales related to health insurance.
- They should increase their net work hospitals.
- They should simplify their claim procedures.
- They should reduce documentation.

Conclusion:

Expectations and utilization among policy holders are rapidly evolving and tending toward greater customization. In order to generate service value, it is crucial for service providers across all industry segments to monitor consumer behavior and purchasing trends. The retail sector is a prime example of monitoring consumer activity and giving personalized alerts. It is recommended that health insurance carriers adopt technologically advanced communication techniques to establish enduring relationships and raise awareness among policy holders. In order to ensure that Indians are aware of their right to obtain high-quality healthcare without having to worry about their financial situation, it is imperative that the government and other related entities encourage the development of health insurance awareness. Additionally, it will support raising health insurance awareness and usage among the policyholders.

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